

REVISION OF ENHANCED RECOVERY AFTER SURGERY (ERAS) PATHWAY FOLLOWING BLADDER SURGERY

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Background and Problem

- Urinary bladder cancer is 6th most common cancer in the USA
- In 2015 – 74,000 new cases
56,320 – males & 17,680 – females (Siegel, Miller, & Jemal, 2015)
- ERAS – standardized method of care
 - multi-modal & multi-disciplinary
 - improves recovery post-radical cystectomy (Azhar et al., 2016)
- Inconsistent documentation & communication
- Lack of Clinical Practice Guidelines (CPG)

Purpose

- Update ERAS pathway to include CPG
- Improve documentation & communication

Method

- Setting:**
 - 2 Medical-Surgical Units
 - Tertiary cancer hospital
- Data Collection:**
 - Post radical cystectomy in-patients with muscle invasive bladder cancer 50 years & over both males & females
- Procedure:**
 - Data abstraction from 20 random charts: August – November 2016 & 2017
 - 5 ERAS Components:
 - Early mobilization
 - Early oral feeding
 - DVT prophylaxis
 - Post-op ileus prevention
 - Post-op analgesia
 - Clinical Practice Guidelines
- 4 Phases of Project Design:**
 - Input
 - Output
 - Implementation and Adoption
 - Sustainability

Logic Model

Results

Revised 2017 ERAS Pathway with CPG

Operationalized in the form of order sets and included current CPG recommendations, and improve documentation related to completion of the ERAS pathway. These recommendations assisted providers and the staff in decision-making during post-RARC patient care.

Findings

EXPONENTIAL IMPROVEMENTS IN THE POST-INTERVENTION PERIOD:

- Reduction of 30 day readmission rates, LOS, complications, increase patient satisfaction & return of bowel activity at a shorter time.
- Decrease Readmissions from 30% to 5%.
- Decrease average LOS from 12 to 6 days.
- Decrease DVT incidence from 13% to 0%.
- Decrease post-op ileus from 50% to 10%.
- Increase completion of early mobilization from 85% to 95%.
- Completion of early oral feeding increased from 65% to 95%.
- Increased patient satisfaction from 84 % to 92%.

Conclusions

- Improvement in documentation & communication related to ERAS pathway completion evident.
- Post-RARC care & improvement in outcomes optimized in post-intervention period.

Limitations

- Pilot project & short period
- May be non-sustainable
- Possible bias
- Small sample size

Implications

- Development of culture of team work & accountability
- Improved decision-making & workflow
- Revised ERAS pathway will continue to evolve
- Patients empowered and motivated in their plan of care from post-op day zero until day of discharge per ERAS pathway.